

Reactions of 3-Phenylimino-2-indolinone with Carboxylic Acid Hydrazides

RAJENDRA S. VARMA

Chemistry Department, Lucknow University, Lucknow-226 007

Manuscript received 31 March 1978, accepted 10 June 1978

Carboxylic acid hydrazides(I) react with 3-phenylimino-2-indolinone(II) to furnish the corresponding 3-hydrazono-2-indolinones(III). In this reaction the 3-phenylimino group in II has been replaced by a benzoyl hydrazono group.

RECENTLY we have observed that the 3-phenylimino group in II could be replaced by other aromatic amines¹. It was therefore considered of interest to see whether this group is also subject to displacement by aromatic benzoic acid hydrazides. In this note the reactions of carboxylic acid hydrazides(I) with 3-phenylimino-2-indolinone(II) are described.

II has been treated with five hydrazides. In each case it has been observed that the 3-phenylimino group in II has been replaced by a benzoyl hydrazono group to yield IIIa. Direct condensation of isatin with I furnished IIIb. The identity of IIIa and IIIb has been established by means of elemental analysis, m.p., m.m.p. and i.r. spectra. The i.r. spectra of III obtained by both the methods were superimposed. With a view to provide additional evidence IIIa(R=H) was treated with formalin and piperidine in equimolar proportions to furnish IV, which was also obtained from IIIb (m.p., m.m.p. and i.r.). The i.r. spectra of III showed characteristic bands due to CO, C=N and NH. In IV CH₂ absorption was present at 2940 cm⁻¹. The ring carbonyl band which is somewhat broad in III became very sharp in IV. The N.M.R. spectrum of IV showed broad bands at 1.45 and 2.53, assigned to

three methylene protons remote from nitrogen and two methylene protons adjacent to nitrogen of the piperidine ring, respectively. A sharp singlet at 4.4 has been attributed to N—CH₂—N protons. Aromatic protons absorbed at 6.86-7.96 whereas resonance due to CONH was observed at 13.78.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 177 spectrometer, in KBr. N.M.R. spectrum was run in CDCl₃ on a Varian A60D instrument using TMS as an internal standard. Chemical shifts are in δ ppm.

3-Phenylimino-2-indolinone(II) was obtained according to published procedure².

3-Benzoylhydrazono-2-indolinone(III) :

Method A : Isatin (1.47 g) was dissolved in 25 ml of boiling ethanol. Benzoic acid hydrazide (1.36 g) was added to it in small portions with shaking. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 2 hr. The product thus separated was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried in air.

Method B : II (2.22 g) prepared from aniline and isatin and 4-nitrobenzoic acid hydrazide (1.81 g) were suspended in ethanol (25 ml) containing two drops of acetic acid. The reaction mixture was heated under reflux for 2 hr, cooled and filtered. The product was repeatedly washed with ethanol.

All the five compounds listed in Table 1 were prepared by both the methods. Their i.r. spectra were perfectly superimposed.

1-Piperidinomethyl-3-benzoylhydrazono-2-indolinone(IV) :

III(R=H, 2.65 g) was suspended in hot ethanol (25 ml). Formalin (2 ml) and piperidine (0.85 g) were added to it. The reaction mixture was heated on a water bath for 5 min. and thereafter allowed to remain at room temp. overnight. Crude IV thus

R=H, 2-OH, 4-OH, 4-NO₂, 4-NHCOMe

TABLE 1.—3-BENZOYLHYDRAZONO-2-INDOLINONES(III)

No.	R	M.P. °C.	Yield %	Molecular Formula	% N Calcd.	% N Found
1. ^a	H	278	75	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₃	—	—
2. ^b	2-OH	>250	70	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₄	—	—
3.	4-OH	>255	65	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₄	14.95	14.46
4.	4-NHCOCH ₃	>255	60	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₃	17.39	17.61
5.	4-NO ₂	>265	70	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₄	18.06	18.40

a, Lit^a m.p. 279°; b, Lit^a m.p. 326°.

I.R. (cm⁻¹): 3: 3458 (OH), 3165 (NH), 1680 (CO, amide), 1710 (CO, ring).

4: 3315, 3200 (NH), 1665 (CO, amide), 1715 (CO, ring).

5: 3200 (NH), 1665 (CO, amide), 1725 (CO, ring).

obtained was recrystallised from carbon tetrachloride-petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°), m.p. 142-43°, yield 60%. I.R.: 32.0(NH), 2940 (CH₂), 1700 (CO, ring), 1680 cm⁻¹ (CONH); N.M.R.: 1.45

(CH₂CH₂CH₂), 2.53 (N $\begin{matrix} \text{CH}_2 \\ \diagdown \\ \text{CH}_2 \end{matrix}$), 4.40 (N-CH₂-N),

6.86-7.96 (Ar-H), 13.78 (CONH). (Found: N, 15.07%. Calcd. for C₂₁H₂₂N₄O₂: N, 15.47%.

4-N-Acetylaminobenzoic Acid Hydrazide :

Methyl ester of 4-aminobenzoic acid (15.7 g), acetic anhydride (15 ml) and glacial acetic acid (15 ml) were refluxed for 30 min. The contents

were poured on crushed ice and the solid product was filtered washed with water and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 127°, yield 70%. Hydrazine hydrate 99% (2 ml) and methyl-N-acetyl-4-aminobenzoate (4.0 g) were refluxed in ethanol (25 ml) for 10 hr. The contents were cooled and the hydrazide thus separated was washed with ethanol, benzene and petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°), m.p. 270-72°, yield 65%. Due to its extreme insolubility in common organic solvents an analytically pure sample could not be prepared. It was, therefore, characterised by transforming it to N-(2'-hydroxybenzylidene) derivative which recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 282° (Found: N, 14.66%. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₅N₃O₃: N, 14.14%.

Acknowledgement

Thanks of the author are due to Dr. R. S. Kapil for elemental/spectral data and to the Head of the Chemistry Department for providing departmental facilities.

References

1. R. S. VARMA and I. A. KHAN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, (In press).
2. I. A. KHAN, Ph.D. Thesis, Lucknow University, 1977.
3. Beilsteins Handbuch Der Organischen Chemie, Verlag Von Julius Springer, Berlin, 1935, Vol. 21, p. 445.
4. N. P. BUU-HOI, N. D. XUONG, N. H. NAM, F. BINON and R. ROYER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 1358.